

Corrigendum to Zhang *et al.* (2020): “New *Eostrobilops* Pilsbry, 1927 (Eupulmonata: Strobilopsidae) of China”

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In the publication describing *Eostrobilops wuranicus* Zhang, 2020 several errors were unnoticed until after publication (Zhang *et al.* 2020). The scale bar was missing in Figure 1, and an arrow was missing in Figure 2. Corrected versions of these figures are republished on the following pages. Some data in the Table 1 were mistakenly written. This table is corrected here. The taxonomic remarks should be corrected to indicate that *E. kongoensis* (Kuroda & Miyanaga, 1939) has more lamella than *E. wuranicus*. On the page 547, *E. coreanus* was mistakenly spelled as *E. koreans*.

Thanks go to Dr Larisa Prozorova for pointing out these errors.

REFERENCE

ZHANG G, QIU X, LIU T. 2020. New *Eostrobilops* Pilsbry, 1927 (Eupulmonata: Strobilopsidae) of China. *Journal of Conchology* **43** (5): 543–548.

Table 1. Inner shell structures of *Eostrobilops* distributed in Russia, Korea, and Japan.

<i>Eostrobilops</i>	Folds	Lamella	Distribution	References
<i>E. coreanus coreanus</i> (Pilsbry, 1927)	4	3	Pyong, Korea; Cedar, Russia	Pilsbry 1927; Schileyko 1984
<i>E. coreanus echo</i> (Kuroda & Miyanaga, 1939)	4	3	outer Kumgang Mountains, Korea	Kuroda & Miyanaga 1939
<i>E. diodontinus</i> (Heude, 1885)	—	—	Chengkou, Chongqing, China	Heude 1885
<i>E. hirasei</i> (Pilsbry, 1908)	2	3	Quelpart Island, Korea	Pilsbry 1908
<i>E. humicolus</i> Páll-Gergely & Hunyadi, 2015	3	4	Hechi, Guangxi, China	Páll-Gergely et al. 2015
<i>E. kanjiokuboi</i> (Minato & Tada, 1992)	3	2	Nantou, Taiwan, China	Minato & Tada 1992
<i>E. kongoensis</i> (Kuroda & Miyanaga, 1939)	4–5	3	Kumgang Mountains, Korea	Kuroda & Miyanaga 1939
<i>E. nipponicus nipponicus</i> (Pilsbry, 1927)	3–5	3	Yonezawa, Japan	Pilsbry 1927
<i>E. nipponicus reikoa</i> Matsumura & Minato, 1998	3	2	Takatsuki-shi, Osaka, Japan	Matsumura & Mino 1998
<i>E. taiwanicus</i> (Minato & Tada, 1992)	3	2	Nantou, Taiwan, China	Minato & Tada 1992
<i>E. wuranicus</i> Zhang, n. sp.	4	2	Yantai or Weihai, Shandong, China	This study
<i>E. yaeyamensis</i> (Habe & Chinen, 1974)	2–3	2	Irimote Island, Ishigaki Island, Japan	Habe & Chinen 1974
<i>E. zijinshanicus</i> Chen, 2019	3	3	Nanjing, Jiangsu, China	Chen 2019

Figure 1. Dorsal (apical), apertural, lateral and umbilical view of the holotype of *Eostrobilops wuranicus*. Arrows point to basal folds. Scale bar = 1 mm.

Figure 2. A, C, holotype of *Eostrobilops nipponicus nipponicus*. B, D, holotype of *E. coreanus coreanus*. E, inner shell structure of *E. wuranicus* (SDNU.GAS.0221.01.04). Arrows point to basal folds. Scale bar = 1mm.